

RED TEAMING GENERATIVE AI APPLICATIONS: THREAT MODELING AND MITIGATION STRATEGIES

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Abstract: *As generative AI systems grow in adoption and complexity, they introduce novel security, safety and alignment risks that challenge traditional evaluation and defense paradigms. To address these, we focus on a structured five-phase red teaming workflow consisting of reconnaissance, enumeration, exploitation, impact realization and persistence specifically tailored to GenAI's unique threat landscape. Through real-world case studies and examples, we illustrate how adversaries exploit model vulnerabilities, bypass alignment mechanisms and cause persistent harm. We also identify emerging GenAI security tools and map each red teaming phase to actionable mitigations that support safe deployment. Our goal is to connect AI safety theory with practical adversarial resilience for researchers, developers and policymakers.*

Keywords: *Generative AI, AI red teaming, prompt injection, jailbreak attacks, RAG security, AI safety, offensive security, cybersecurity, LLM vulnerabilities.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Generative AI (GenAI) is a rapidly evolving subfield of artificial intelligence focused on the autonomous creation of new content, including images, music, text and even complex virtual environments. At its core, it aims to produce diverse, coherent and novel outputs that often resemble human-generated artifacts (Huang et al., 2024). As businesses and governments increasingly integrate GenAI into critical systems (e.g. healthcare and finance) the risks associated with its misuse or malfunction have grown in importance.

These risks span reputational damage, legal liability, data leakage, algorithmic bias and even national security threats. In recognition of these dangers, AI red teaming was defined in the U.S. Presidential Executive Order as a structured testing effort to find flaws and vulnerabilities in an AI system, often in a controlled environment and in collaboration with developers of AI (Executive Office of the President, 2023).

AI red teaming, by design, moves beyond static model benchmarks and alignment metrics by emulating attacks against end-to-end systems in realistic deployment settings (Bullwinkel et al., 2025). Major companies such as Microsoft, Anthropic and OpenAI have established growing internal AI red teams, while community led efforts such as the DEF CON Red Team Challenge (Hack the Future, 2025) and Prompt Airlines Capture-the-Flag (Wiz.io, 2025) competitions reflect growing interest in adversarial evaluation. However, a significant gap persists between the priorities of AI red teams in practice and the focus of academic researchers, especially regarding deployment threats and holistic system testing (Apruzzese et al., 2023; Boenisch et al., 2021; Sun et al., 2021).

This paper presents case studies and outlines a five-phase red teaming workflow tailored to GenAI. Drawing from offensive security principles and adapted for AI, this structured approach aims to uncover, understand and mitigate system-level vulnerabilities before they can be exploited.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews the current state of AI red teaming and relevant tools. Section 3 introduces our proposed five-phase workflow. Section 4 presents case studies and phase-specific mitigations. We conclude the paper with Section 5 listing key takeaways and recommendations for safe development of GenAI powered systems.

2. STATE OF AI RED TEAMING

Red teaming in machine learning (ML) has a rich history, with early efforts focusing on traditional natural language processing systems (Dai et al., 2019; Wallace et al., 2019) and computer vision models (Elsayed et

al., 2018). These attacks often relied on sophisticated technical manipulations, such as adversarial image perturbations (Poursaeed et al., 2018), that required deep domain knowledge. However, the landscape changed dramatically with the release of large-scale generative models accessible through natural language interfaces in late 2022. This democratization of generative AI tools has enabled a wider range of users, including those without formal technical backgrounds, to explore, manipulate and adversarially test ML systems in novel ways (Inie et al., 2023).

This shift in accessibility has increased the interest in adversarial interactions with generative AI, especially large language models (LLMs). Researchers have begun to systematize red teaming strategies for LLMs, examining their susceptibility to various forms of manipulation and misuse (Perez et al., 2022). A prominent category of such adversarial behavior is known as jailbreaking, where users attempt to bypass safety mechanisms or policy enforced restrictions imposed by model developers (Russovich et al., 2024; Zhou et al., 2024). These jailbreak attempts mirror classic security paradigms such as privilege escalation, adapted to the unique constraints of generative models. While jailbreaks can be used for legitimate research and safety testing, they also raise significant ethical, legal and security concerns (Raheja et al., 2024).

As the adoption of generative AI accelerates across industries, the need for systematic approaches to security and risk mitigation has become critical. Several tools have been developed specifically for this purpose, aiming to simulate real-world adversarial behaviors and stress-test AI models under malicious or edge-case scenarios. For example, NVIDIA's Garak (Derczynski et al., 2024) serves as a vulnerability scanner tailored for LLMs and is analogous to traditional cybersecurity tools like Nmap or Metasploit.

In parallel with tool development, foundational frameworks have emerged to help contextualize threats and guide red teaming efforts. The OWASP Top 10 for LLMs (OWASP Foundation, 2025), adapted from the original web security list, identifies common risks in LLM applications, including prompt injection, data exposure and unchecked reliance on AI-generated content. It is increasingly used to shape best practices in enterprise and regulatory contexts.

The AI Incident Database (AIID) (Responsible AI Collaborative, 2024a), maintained by the Partnership on AI, complements these frameworks by cataloging real-world cases of AI misuse, failure and ethical breaches. These incidents serve as practical references for improving red teaming strategies and designing effective mitigations.

Together, these tools and frameworks establish a foundation for generative AI security by supporting early vulnerability detection, realistic threat modeling and proactive mitigation, while also aiding regulatory compliance (Christodorescu et al., 2024). However, existing resources such as MITRE ATLAS (MITRE Corporation, 2021), designed for AI red teaming, lack an integrated, phase-based framework specifically tailored to the unique challenges of GenAI. In response, this paper synthesizes existing knowledge and introduces a structured five-phase workflow, grounded in documented attack scenarios, to offer practitioners and researchers practical guidance for thorough security assessment and effective mitigation.

3. STRUCTURED RED TEAMING WORKFLOW FOR GENAI SYSTEMS

This section goes over the five most important phases in a red teaming workflow, tailored to the characteristics and deployment of GenAI systems. This workflow draws inspiration from classical offensive security phases (Dalalana Bertoglio and Zorzo, 2017; Sawant and Chopra, 2023; Süren et al., 2023) as well as existing AI red teaming frameworks (Feffer et al., 2024; MITRE Corporation, 2013) and is structured into five key stages: Reconnaissance, Enumeration, Exploitation, Impact Realization and Persistence, as illustrated in Figure 1. Each stage captures a distinct aspect of the adversarial interaction with a generative model or its surrounding ecosystem. The methodology is designed to allow researchers, developers and security teams to adapt it to various use cases including chatbots, code assistants, agentic systems and RAG architectures.

The **reconnaissance** phase focuses on collecting openly available information about the target model and deployment environment. Adversaries often leverage technical platforms such as GitHub, Hugging Face or ArXiv to obtain model cards, training references or system design artifacts (Bullwinkel et al., 2025). Additional intelligence may be gathered from API documentation or changelogs, which can expose input formatting, integration logic or hidden prompt structures. Attackers may also engage in model fingerprinting through crafted queries to infer model family, fine-tuning presence or the use of Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG).

In the **enumeration** phase, attackers actively probe the system to map its behavioral boundaries and identify implemented safety mechanisms. This includes prompt experimentation to test alignment responses, format sensitivity and prompt injection susceptibility. Common enumeration strategies include direct and indirect prompt injection (S. Chen et al., 2024), where the model is tricked into ignoring system instructions

or processing hidden adversarial inputs. Techniques like context flooding may also be used to push alignment prompts out of scope, particularly in systems with constrained context windows.

In the **exploitation** phase, attackers actively leverage vulnerabilities identified during earlier stages to induce malicious, unintended or policy-violating behavior from the generative model or its supporting infrastructure. Exploitation techniques range from classical jailbreaks to more advanced forms of attack such as RAG poisoning (Deng et al., 2024). Unlike the exploratory probing of the enumeration phase, exploitation produces concrete outputs that demonstrate the feasibility and impact of a security failure, often serving as a precursor to measurable harm in downstream applications.

The **impact realization** phase focuses on demonstrating the tangible consequences of successful exploitation, particularly in real-world deployments. At this stage, theoretical vulnerabilities become observable harm, such as misinformation, unauthorized access or the generation of unsafe output. These strategies can affect downstream applications and erode trust in model integrity, highlighting the broader technical and social implications of successful attacks.

Finally, the **persistence** phase evaluates whether discovered vulnerabilities remain stable across sessions, model updates or deployment environments. While generative models exhibit probabilistic behavior, attackers aim to identify reliable failure modes, such as repeatable jailbreak prompts or robust RAG poisoning payloads. Persistence may also stem from dataset poisoning (Goldblum et al., 2022), where malicious behaviors are encoded during training or fine-tuning and survive subsequent mitigation efforts. In agentic systems, long-term memory modules may retain compromised data that influences future interactions, embedding the exploit into the agent’s behavioral history (Z. Chen et al., 2024).

Figure 1: The five phases in red teaming for Generative AI systems

4. CASE STUDIES AND MITIGATION STRATEGIES

In this section, we present real-world case studies aligned with each phase of the AI red teaming lifecycle. Each phase features carefully selected incidents from reputable sources, such as the AIID and MITRE ATLAS, chosen to highlight specific attack strategies relevant to that stage. For each phase, we also provide mitigation techniques to help practitioners proactively anticipate, detect and respond to emerging threats. A summary of representative attack–mitigation examples for each phase is provided in Table 1.

4.1. Reconnaissance - Understanding the Target

Case Study 1: Researchers reverse engineered Cylance’s AI-powered malware detection by analyzing public information, such as research papers and patents. Using this data, they built a surrogate model to mimic the target system, ultimately crafting malware that bypassed detection (MITRE Corporation, 2019).

Case Study 2: The Sysdig Threat Research Team discovered that attackers gained unauthorized access to cloud-hosted LLMs via compromised credentials, which is a tactic known as “LLM jacking.” They mapped exposed model endpoints and reverse proxied access for resale (Responsible AI Collaborative, 2024b).

Mitigation Strategies: Reducing the availability of technical and organizational details can limit attackers ability to develop accurate threat models. Minimizing public exposure and controlling internal access points increases uncertainty for potential attackers, making it harder for them to plan effective intrusions.

4.2. Enumeration - Probing for System Behaviour

Case Study 3: Attackers tested a range of prompt injection techniques against Microsoft Bing Chat by embedding hidden prompts in web pages. One successful method involved rendering invisible text (e.g. using a font size of zero), which the chatbot processed when users visited the page. This allowed attackers to trigger unintended behaviors, such as exfiltrating private user data or manipulating responses without the user’s awareness or consent (Greshake et al., 2023).

Mitigation Strategies: By shaping how systems respond to patterns of interaction, it’s possible to reduce the clarity and consistency that attackers rely on. Embedding constraints into system behavior (Rai et al., 2024) and maintaining awareness of interaction patterns can help preserve operational integrity while limiting opportunities for exploitation.

4.3. Exploitation - Triggering Harmful Behavior

Case Study 4: Fraudsters used deepfake video conferencing to impersonate a company’s CFO and staff, convincing a finance employee to transfer \$25 million. Every participant in the call was an AI-generated fake, demonstrating the risks of generative AI in multimodal fraud scenarios (CNN, 2024).

Case Study 5: An LLM hallucinated the existence of a non-existent package, called “huggingface-cli”, prompting attackers to publish a real malicious version under that name. The package was downloaded over 15,000 times, illustrating a novel supply chain vulnerability - “slopsquatting” (Spracklen et al., 2024).

Mitigation Strategies: Enhancing system resilience through diverse training, structural safeguards and informed development practices can reduce susceptibility. Maintaining awareness of interaction anomalies and reinforcing the system’s ability to resist manipulation helps preserve trust and stability in deployment.

4.4. Impact Realization - Manifesting Consequences

Case Study 6: Microsoft’s chatbot Tay was overwhelmed by toxic user input shortly after deployment. The model quickly began producing offensive content, leading to its removal from public access (BBC News, 2016).

Case Study 7: The ROME algorithm demonstrated how attackers could surgically alter factual knowledge embedded in a model’s weights. Such tampering can cause the model to persistently generate false information (e.g. attributing the discovery of America to a fictional character) (Meng et al., 2022).

Mitigation Strategies: Ensuring that systems remain aligned with intended behaviors, while enabling detection and response to deviations, helps contain potential consequences. Thoughtful design and operational discipline are key to limiting the materialization of adverse outcomes.

4.5. Persistence - Maintaining a Foothold

Case Study 8: A persistent vulnerability involving prompt injection in ChatGPT’s “Memory” feature allowed attackers to store spyware-like instructions that exfiltrated user data across conversations. The exploit used third-party websites to inject malicious memory entries, which would continuously relay chat data to an attacker controlled server via image rendering URLs even across sessions (Rehberger, 2024b).

Case Study 9: Another persistence risk emerged through ChatGPT’s Browsing tool. Researchers demonstrated that by embedding specific prompts within websites, ChatGPT could be tricked into automatically invoking internal tools such as DALLE (for image generation) or the Memory tool (for reading/writing long-term user data). For example, websites were able to erase existing user memories (Rehberger, 2024a).

Mitigation Strategies: Safeguarding the model lifecycle against embedded threats requires sustained oversight and infrastructure integrity. Proactive governance supports resilience against long-term compromise. Ensuring traceability is critical to preserving alignment and trustworthiness over time.

Table 1: Phases, associated attacks and mitigations for secure system design

Phase	Attacks	Mitigation Strategies
Reconnaissance	Model fingerprinting, Information gathering	Limit detail exposure, Monitor system access, Control research visibility
Enumeration	Prompt injections, Context flooding, Behavioral boundary mapping	Rate limiting, Output randomization and filters, Anomaly detection
Exploitation	Jailbreaking, RAG poisoning, Deep- fake impersonation	Ensemble modeling, Adversarial training, Input sanitization
Impact Realization	Knowledge tempering, Toxic content production, Trust erosion	Continuous model integrity validation, Logging
Persistence	Dataset poisoning, Cross-session exploitation	Secure cloud deployment, Cryptographic artifact verification

5. CONCLUSION

As generative AI systems rapidly advance in scale and complexity, ensuring their security and reliability has become an important concern. Traditional static evaluation methods are insufficient for the complex and often subtle failures that characterize modern GenAI applications. In response, red teaming has evolved from a specialized security activity into a foundational component of responsible GenAI development.

This paper has outlined five most important phases in GenAI red teaming: reconnaissance, enumeration, exploitation, impact realization and persistence. Real-world case studies illustrate that attackers are already exploiting generative systems at scale, with consequences ranging from misinformation to financial fraud. This structured approach equips practitioners, developers and policymakers with an adaptive model for red teaming GenAI systems across use cases.

To counteract these risks, we proposed a multilayered defense strategy aligned with each phase of the adversarial lifecycle. These include reducing public information exposure, implementing robust prompt filtering, deploying adversarial training and establishing strong governance over data, model artifacts and system deployment. Together, these measures offer a comprehensive guide for building more secure and trustworthy generative AI systems.

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